

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF MINI TRACTOR OPERATED INTER ROW WEEDER: A CONCEPT

H. D. Nahate¹ P. B. Kadam² S. K. Thakare³

Department of Farm Power and Machinery, Dr. A.S.College of Agril. Engg. & Technology, MPKV, Rahuri (M.S)

1. PhD Scholar, Department of Farm Power and Machinery, Dr. A.S.C.A.E.T, MPKV, Rahuri.

harishnahate@gmail.com

2. Associate Professor: Department of Farm Power and Machinery, Dr. A.S.C.A.E.T, MPKV, Rahuri, Maharashtra, India.

3. Assistant Professor: Department of Farm Power and Machinery, Dr. PDKV, Akola, Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract

A weed is any plant not intentionally sown or propagated by the grower that requires management to prevent it from interfering with crop or livestock production. In peak period farmer faces problems of labour for manual weeding and sometimes weed infestation is out of control for manual labour. Due to this weed infestation occurs at high intensity. Farmers are unable to do intercultural operation due to unavailability of labour and their high wages. To avoid this weed has to be controlled by mechanical means by taking into consideration of following agronomic concept. When the weed is cut by using the appropriate equipment at some height above ground level can be useful for mulching and other benefits to the plants. For this purpose, a mini tractor operated weed shredder is the need of the time and proposes to develop weed shredder to be operated by low hp tractor.

Key Words: Farm mechanization, Definition of Weed, Weed as mulch, Inter Row weeder, Arrangement of blades.

Introduction

The term “weed” has been defined as a “plant out of place,” an “unwanted plant,” or a plant that is a pest in that it interferes with crop or livestock production. The word is typically applied to any plant species that often becomes a pest, such as common chickweed, pigweeds or crabgrass.

Weeds are nature’s way of covering soil that has become exposed by fire, flood, landslide, windstorms, clear-cutting, clean tillage, herbicides, overgrazing, or other disturbance. Bare soil is hungry and at risk. The soil life, so vital to soil fertility, goes hungry because the normal influx of nourishing organic compounds from living plant roots has been cut off for the time being. The exposed soil surface is at risk of erosion by rain or wind, especially if root systems have also been removed or disrupted. Pioneer plants – weeds – are those species that can rapidly cover bare soil and begin performing a number of vital ecological functions:

Protect the soil from erosion.

Replenish organic matter, feed and restore soil life.

Absorb, conserve, and recycle soluble nutrients that would otherwise leach away.

Absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere.

Restore biodiversity.

Provide habitat for insects and animals.

Mulching is the process of covering the topsoil with plant material such as leaves, grass, twigs, crop residues, straw etc. A mulch cover enhances the activity of soil organisms such as earthworms. They help to create a soil structure with plenty of smaller and larger pores through which rainwater can easily infiltrate into the soil, thus reducing surface runoff. As the mulch material decomposes, it increases the content of organic matter in the soil. Soil organic matter helps to create a good soil with stable crumb structure. Thus the soil particles will not be easily carried away by water. Therefore, mulching plays a crucial role in preventing soil erosion. Protecting the soil from wind and water erosion soil particles cannot be washed or blown away. The other benefits are as follows:

Improving the infiltration of rain and irrigation water by maintaining a good soil structure: no crust is formed, the pores are kept open.

Keeping the soil moist by reducing evaporation: plants need less irrigation or can use the available rain more efficiently in dry areas or seasons.

Feeding and protecting soil organisms: organic mulch material is an excellent food for soil organisms and provides suitable conditions for their growth.

Suppressing weed growth: with a sufficient mulch layer, weeds will find it difficult to grow through it.

Preventing the soil from heating up too much: mulch provides shade to the soil and the retained moisture keeps it cool.

Providing nutrients to the crops: while decomposing, organic mulch material continuously releases its nutrients, thus fertilizing the soil.

Increasing the content of soil organic matter: part of the mulch material will be trans-formed to humus.

Material and Methods**Power source**

A newly developed weeder is propose to be operated by 25-30 hp small tractors. The implement should be work properly for a 25 - 30 HP tractor , that will be decide on the basis of moisture content in soil, type of weed to cut and, Kind of crop sown.

Specification of Weeder

The propose weeder of the width is 1180 mm and height 1280 mm in order to cover a two rows while weeding.

Spring suspension

To adjust height of cutting the weeds the implement should have spring suspension to adjust the height of cut.

Hitch Category

CAT II type category hitch will be used in the implement. The implement should be attached to the three point linkage of the tractor of different HP, so the implement should have design dimensions to match perfectly with the three point linkage for different HP tractors.

Blade

The L Type heavy blade is propose in order to cut the weed just above the ground level so it should be sharp enough to cut the weeds by impact force. The position of blades on flange should be anti-parallel to each other.

Frame

Frame should be made of M.S Angle. The arrangement for attaching implements to the tractor will be rest on this Frame. It should be reliable.

Gear Box

High carbon steel, beveled gear is used in this equipment for power transfer from tractor PTO to implement. Gear box should be such that it will give 2000 RPM in order to fast cutting of weed in the rows.

Chain and sprocket arrangement

This mechanism will give power transmission from gear box to blade rotor. Half inch double stand chain may prefer for this arrangement. The proposed chain length is of chain 1524 mm.

Performance evaluation of weeder**Agronomical Parameters****Crop**

- Row spacing
- Height of crop plant

Weed

- Kind, variety of weed.
- Height of weed.

Field test

- Moisture content
- Bulk density
- Cone index
- Speed of operation

5. Effective field capacity
6. Theoretical field capacity
7. Field efficiency
8. Forward speed

9. Fuel consumption
10. Plant damage
11. Weeding efficiency

Fig. 1 Proposed inter row weeder

Table 1 Specification of Weeder:

Sr. No	Particulars	Specification requirement
1	Main Frame	80×80×5 mm, Length 1995 mm
2	Gear box	Crown & Pinion gearbox, 1:4 speed ratio
3	Power source	35 hp, small tractor
4	Overall width	1280 mm
5	Overall height	1180 mm
6	Hitch category	CAT I, CAT II, Three Point Linkage
7	Working Width	450 mm per row
8	Chain and sprocket arrangement	25 teeth, half inch double stand chain (1524 mm chain length)
9	Type of Blade	Inter row "L" Type
10	No of blades	24
10	Depth Controller	Spring suspension
11	Weight of implement	350 kgs
12	Overall length	1995 mm
13	RPM of gearbox	Depends on input (2000 rpm)
14	Support wheel	1200 mm height, 300 mm wheel diameter
15	Main shaft	1995 mm length, 50×50 cross section
16	Rotor shaft	32 mm dia. × 795.56 mm length
17	Blade size	100 mm length × 50 mm width, 5 mm thickness

Comparison of performance with the existing weeding practices

Work rate and labour requirements

- a) Operating speed
- b) Actual operating hours
- c) Time spent for adjustment of machine
- d) Time spent for machine trouble
- e) Working capacity
- f) Number of workers and man hour required for machine and manual weeding.

Based on the above data, the area covered and the cost of operation can be calculated.

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